

ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT, WORKPLACE SPIRITUALITY AND TEAM EFFECTIVENESS: A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL ON SERVICE QUALITY OF BARANGAY HEALTH WORKERS

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Abstract

Service quality in community healthcare encountered shortages of workers, as well as insufficient facilities and services. Despite extensive research on service quality, there remains a dearth of literature exploring models that incorporate organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, and team effectiveness. This research employs a quantitative causal method by utilizing a structural equation model (SEM) to establish the best-fit model for understanding the interplay of variables. The findings revealed a significant relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables. The findings also depicted that the generated model 3 was the best-fit model and successfully passed all the tests for a reasonable fit.

Keywords: Service Quality, Organizational Commitment, Workplace Spirituality, Team Effectiveness, Structural Equation Model, Barangay Health Workers.

1. INTRODUCTION

Service quality continues to be an uphill journey in community healthcare because it faces challenges primarily stemming from an imbalance between demand and supply, significantly impacting the desired outcomes in community healthcare provision. It is the level of care and services for the people increase the desired health results. Lack of service quality will result in undesirable outcomes such as shortages of workers, patient death and suffering, distrust, financial difficulties, unequal distribution of care, and poor management and communication, among others. Aytona, et al. (2022) mentioned that service quality is a cause of concern worldwide, particularly among developing countries like the Philippines, since quality health services can only be delivered to people with a sufficient and competent health workforce, and to minimize the shortages of health workers and maldistribution that resulted in disparities in providing quality health care service. Service quality is vital in healthcare management and operation for patient care and safety. Vu (2021) tells us that service quality is important relative to patient satisfaction, which is widely recognized for long-term goals and customer loyalty. Each time the components of service quality are delivered, there will be more trust and faster healing with less pain, tension, and anxiety on the part of the patients.

Theoretical framework and scientific studies emphasize that organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, and team effectiveness have some link to service quality. Over the years, some scholars have continuously explored better frameworks and models that address service quality goals. Abdul-Majid, et al. (2022); and Adam and Kesuma (2022) attributed service

quality to organizational commitment, and organizations must focus on the employees' commitment to enhance service delivery. Meanwhile, Rajain & Rathee (2020) and Jnaneswas (2021) linked service quality to workplace spirituality, in which the workforce will have better organizational performance, job involvement, commitment, and overall satisfaction because of spiritual care or workplace spirituality within the company. Further, Chakraborty, et al. (2021) and Brom et al. (2021) connected service quality with team effectiveness, in which the morale, confidence, and competence developed by the team will affect patient care, especially the essential services.

From the above context, the researcher pursued this study with three exogenous variables that may influence service quality: organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, and team effectiveness. There is a dearth of literature and no study yet exploring models incorporating organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, and team effectiveness and its effects on service quality, specifically concerning barangay health workers (BHWs) in Region XII, Philippines. Further, most of the study locales are in hospital, company, or school settings, and there is a lack of research conducted in the community or barangay setting. This was highlighted in the study of Coombs, Campbell and Caringi (2022) about the barriers to healthcare access particularly in the rural settings. Hence, this research will address the limited studies of service quality of barangay health workers as what Hartigan-Go, et al. (2023) emphasized of their critical roles but often the neglected sector. Additionally, this study will provide an advanced statistical method since it has four variables.

The study's main objective is to identify the best-fit structural model of service quality among Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) in relation to 'organizational commitment', 'workplace spirituality', and team effectiveness. For 'organizational commitment', the study addresses the specific purposes: (1) to describe the level of organizational commitment of BHWs as to 'affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment; (2) to determine the level of workplace spirituality's level of Barangay Health Workers as to compassion, mindfulness, 'meaningful work', and 'transcendence'; (3) to measure the level of team effectiveness of Barangay Health Workers as to 'effective decision-making', 'open communication', 'support and trust', 'honesty', 'effective leadership', 'opportunities for development', 'effective inter-team relationships', 'feedback', 'clear understanding of aims and objectives', and 'conflict management'; (4) to determine the level of service quality of Barangay Health Workers in terms of 'reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles'; (5) to ascertain 'the significance of the relationship between organizational commitment' and service quality; workplace spirituality and service quality; and team effectiveness and service quality; (6) to establish 'the significance of the influence between the exogenous and endogenous variables'; and (7) to find out what model best fits the service quality of barangay health workers.

The study has three hypotheses to be tested at 0.05 level of significance. These are: (1) 'There is no significant relationship between organizational commitment and service quality, workplace spirituality and service quality, and team effectiveness and service quality of BHWs'; (2) There is no significant influence of organizational commitment, workplace

spirituality, and team effectiveness on ‘service quality’ of barangay health workersI; and (3) ‘There is no best fit model for the service quality of barangay health workers’.

This study is anchored on Parasuraman, Berry, Zeithmal’s Service Quality Gap in 1988 that determines the quality of service of the workers within the organizations. This is significant for understanding better customer perception, service expectations, and service improvement (Baharun & Ghotbabadi, 2015). Moreover, based on empirical evidence, Adam, Erfivan, and Kesuma (2022); Hashim and Mahmood (2012); and Cheung (2010) stated that service quality is related to organizational commitment since it was found that both the management and employees who are committed to their work positively affect their satisfaction and customer service. On the other hand, the findings of Almazan, Alharbi, Rivera, and Cruz (2019) and Roger (2014) offer analytical perspectives, which showed that ‘spirituality’ among healthcare providers brings better care provision to the patients, which indicates longer tenure with a therapeutic effect on patients and their families that can produce positive services. Furthermore, Brom, et al. (2021) and Khari and Sinha (2017) highlighted that there is a link between the effectiveness of the team and service quality, specifically in healthcare, where higher nurse-physical teamwork resulted in improved patient outcomes for service quality. Regarding the conceptual framework, the study’s exogenous (independent) variables are organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, and team effectiveness. Service quality is the study’s endogenous (dependent) variable, and the latent variables (not directly observed). Therefore, observed variables or multiple measures are associated with each latent construct by measuring its varying degrees - regression paths.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of the Study

The study is significant to public administration, especially to good governance, public health, as well as the body of knowledge relative to the relationship and modeling of the effects of organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, and team effectiveness on service quality. It is further hoped that the research outcome could have a modest significance and contribution to new knowledge especially UN and ASEAN SDGs particularly ‘SDG 3: Good Health and

Well-Being, and SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth (UNDESA, 2024)'. This study is also significant to our policymakers to enact and implement policies that support better service quality of barangay health workers and among government agencies for better community healthcare delivery. In the academe, this will be helpful in their study as to what behavior is needed for every employee to have a more service oriented organization. Hence, the study will significantly value policy forecasting and program retooling, particularly in improving and enhancing the service quality of BHWs. The research results may serve as repository of data to replicate in other regions.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section presents the methodologies and procedures that is utilized in this research. It includes the study participants, materials and instrument, design, and procedure.

Research Respondents

The respondents involved 456 barangay health workers in Region XII, which was derived from the sample size using the Raosoft calculator. The sample size identified the calculation with '5% margin of error', level of confidence of 99%, and distribution response of 50% for the 1,450 total population. 'Wolf, Harrington, Clark, and Miller (2013), iterated that the sample population for the Structural Equation Model should be between 30 to 460. After determining the total sample population, the researcher employed stratified random sampling for the respondents' selection with a sample size of 456, distributed proportionately to the four cities of the region. The distribution of respondents in the four (4) cities of Region 12: General Santos City has 258 respondents, Kidapawan City has 91 respondents, Tacurong City has 54 respondents, and Koronadal City has 53 respondents, with a total of 456 respondents.

According to Qualtrics (2024), Stratified random sampling is typically used by researchers in survey studies to measure data from different strata or subgroups. The respondents included were the BHWs. They were hired by the City Local Government Units (CLGUs) or Barangay Local Government Units (BLGU) under the City Health Office of each city. They should be accredited barangay health workers (Local Health Board) with continuous active service assigned to render duties to the Barangay Health Centers. The study did not include health workers who were not assigned to the barangay, such as a barangay health nurse, barangay midwife, or a barangay health staff, and who are not managed by the city's BHW coordinator. Furthermore, the participation of the BHWs were voluntary, and an 'Informed Consent Form (ICF)' or UMER-006 was used. They could pull-out at any time without punishment if they decide to discontinue.

Materials and Instrument

The adopted questionnaires were downloaded from electronic sources. The adviser then reviewed the instrument then validated by the pool of experts. The questionnaires were from Allen and Meyer (1990) for organizational commitment. Shrestha (2016) for workplace spirituality, Cook (2015) for team effectiveness, and Lukea-Bhiwajee, Ramscook-Munhurrin, & Naidoo (2010) for service quality. Although the instruments were adapted in several research,

the questionnaires were modified and improved to fit the relevance and purpose of the research. Thirty (30) barangay health workers participated in the 'pilot testing' to ascertain the reliability. The organizational commitment 'instrument obtained a score of 0.792 (Cronbach alpha), with an acceptable consistency; workplace spirituality of 0.739, which is acceptable; team effectiveness of 0.928 interpreted as excellent; and service quality of 0.796 as acceptable (ScienceDirect, 2024).

The validated questionnaire was approved by a pool of internal experts resulting to an excellent score of 4.57. Also, a DPA graduate and a serving as an external expert validated the questionnaire ho is a DPA graduate and an Assumption College of Nabunturan instructor giving it a rating of 5.00. The researcher employed a 5-point Likert-type scale that determines the 'degree of agreement and disagreement of the statements that were modified (Taherdoost, 2019)'. It included the organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, and team effectiveness, and service quality with identified factors. The researcher used the following mean range scale: (1) 4.20-5.00: The measures are always manifested; (2) 3.40-4.19: The measures are often manifested); (c) 2.60-3.39: The measures are sometimes manifested; (d) 1.80-2.59: The measures are seldom manifested; and (e) 1.00-1.79: The measures are almost never manifested.

Design and Procedure

The researcher employed a quantitative, descriptive-correlational method, utilizing the 'structural equation model'. First, this study applied a quantitative, descriptive-correlational research method' to measure the associations of variables at varying degrees of measurement. This study is a quantitative-descriptive type because it is a non-experimental study wherein the variables are measured using numbers or statistics, and the variables under investigation are not manipulated by the researcher (Mburva, 2023). Also, this is also 'descriptive-correlational' because it described 'the variables of the study and analyzed the relationships between and among them (Noah, 2021)'. Second, the researcher likewise utilized the structural equation model (SEM). The model is like regression analysis but more powerful and sophisticated. It measures and analyzes the 'relationships of observed and latent variables, investigating the linear causal relationships between and among variables and accounting for measurement error (Beran & Violato, 2010)'.

For the data computation, 'hypothesis testing at a level of significance of 0.05' was determined. The statistical measurements that were utilized were as follow: (a) 'mean and standard deviation for the level of organizational commitment', workplace spirituality, team effectiveness and service quality of barangay health workers; (b) pearson r for the 'significant relationship between the variables (exogenous and endogenous); (c) regression analysis for the influence of variables; (d) structural equation model for the service quality's 'best fit model'. Furthermore, based on the criteria for the 'Goodness of Fit Standard Statistics for Structural Models', the following were as follow: 'P-Value>0.05', 'Chi Square/Degree of Freedom (CMIN/DF) <5', 'Normative Fit Index (NFI)>0.95', 'Comparative Fit Index (CFI)>0.95', 'Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)>0.95', 'Tucker-Lewis Index>0.95', 'Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)<0.05', and 'P-close 0.05'.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section provides a data presentation, discussion, and analysis of barangay health workers' organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, team effectiveness, and service quality. Also, the significant findings are presented.

Organizational Commitment of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

Table 1 shows that the highest calculated mean score of 4.35, SD=0.42, interpreted as very high, which means that the level of organizational commitment is always manifested among barangay health workers as measured by the indicators of 'affective, continuance, and normative commitments'. Based on the data, normative commitment has the highest score of 4.67 (very high), while continuance commitment garnered the lowest score of 3.98 (high).

Table 1: Level of Organizational Commitment of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Affective Commitment	0.48	4.39	Very High
Continuance Commitment;	0.64	3.98	High
Normative Commitment;	0.49	4.67	Very High
Overall	0.42	4.35	Very High

The data result is coherent with the findings of Fook & Muda (2020) that a committed workforce provides critical advantages to the company, such as lesser worker turnover and higher productivity. Thus, most companies invested substantially in commitment. For the employees to stay loyal and productive, an organization should reciprocate the workforce commitment by providing their needs and desires. If workers are happy in their jobs, there is a corresponding high level of commitment.

Workplace Spirituality of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

Table 2 shows the *level of workplace spirituality among barangay health workers*, focusing on four key indicators - 'compassion', 'meaningful work', 'transcendence', and 'mindfulness'. The total mean score of 4.65 indicates a consistently very high level of *workplace spirituality*. Among the indicators, *transcendence* is the highest with 4.70 mean score while *compassion* has 4.59 which is considered the lowest.

Table 2: Level of Workplace Spirituality of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Compassion	0.47	4.59	Very High
Meaning Work	0.42	4.69	Very High
Transcendence	0.39	4.70	Very High
Mindfulness	0.42	4.62	Very High
Overall	0.34	4.65	Very High

The results on *workplace spirituality* aligns with the study of 'Rathee & Rajain (2020)', who stated that it is about creating a supportive environment for employees to practice their beliefs, leading to improved working relationships, productivity, and a greater sense of safety.

Employers are keen on incorporating spirituality within the organization because of its critical effect on quality, and productivity.

Team Effectiveness of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

The results in Table 3 shows the extent of *team effectiveness* of BHWs in Region 12 with a total mean of 4.50, SD of 0.34 with a very high descriptive rating. All indicators of *team effectiveness* recorded as very high mean scores with *clear understanding of aims and objectives* recorded as the highest (4.65), and *honesty* with the lowest mean (4.20). Hence, *team effectiveness* is always manifested among the BHWs.

Table 3: Level of Team Effectiveness of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Effective Decision-making	0.46	4.60	Very High
Open Communication	0.46	4.58	Very High
Support and Trust	0.43	4.57	Very High
Honesty	0.53	4.20	Very High
Effective Leadership	0.49	4.56	Very High
Opportunities for Development	0.45	4.59	Very High
Effective Inter-team Relationship	0.49	4.50	Very High
Feedback	0.51	4.46	Very High
Clear Understanding of Aims and Objectives	0.45	4.65	Very High
Conflict Management	0.55	4.29	Very High
Overall	0.34	4.50	Very High

The findings of Buljac-Samardzic, Doekhie, and Wijngaarden (2020) supports the findings, who emphasized the importance of *teamwork effectiveness* in healthcare quality and patient care. Improving teamwork is a top priority in healthcare organizations, and it can be enhanced through team interventions. These interventions have a positive impact on performance outcomes like effectiveness, efficiency, and patient safety in diverse healthcare settings.

Service Quality of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

The overall mean of 4.64 in Table 4 indicates a consistently very high *service quality*, which is always manifested. The indicator with the highest mean is *responsiveness*, scoring a reassuring 4.81 while *tangibles* as the lowest with 4.16 mean score.

Table 4: Level of Service Quality of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Reliability	0.36	4.78	Very High
Responsiveness	0.33	4.81	Very High
Assurance	0.35	4.70	Very High
Empathy	0.38	4.74	Very High
Tangible	0.61	4.16	High
Overall	0.29	4.64	Very High

This findings of Jain (2021) and Hiranmou and Upadhyal (2020) is coherent with the study, who said that a customer-centric view of healthcare *service quality* that includes patient safety and clinical effectiveness apart from patient experience, focusing on compassion, dignity, and

respect. The quality of healthcare services shows specificity, effectiveness, people and time-centered.

Significance of the Relationship between Organizational Commitment and Service Quality of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

The results in Table 5.1 showed that the ‘correlation coefficient R-value’ was 0.427 with <0.05 P-value to which the null hypothesis was rejected. Since the value met all the criteria to which the significance of a relationship should be tested at the level of 0.05; hence, the computed value establishes a link between *the variables* (‘organizational commitment’ and *service quality*”).

Table 5.1: Significance of the Relationship between Organizational Commitment and Service Quality of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

Organizational Commitment	Service Quality					
	Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Empathy	Tangibles	Overall
Affective Commitment	.217** .000	.219** .000	.236** .000	.247** .000	.258** .000	.331** .000
Continuance Commitment	.226** .000	.198** .000	.285** .000	.231** .000	.176** .000	.302** .000
Normative Commitment	.392** .000	.331** .000	.298** .000	.298** .000	.163** .000	.388** .000
Overall	.347** .000	.310** .000	.348** .000	.325** .000	.249** .000	.427** .000

This shows that increasing ‘organizational commitment’, specifically in areas of ‘affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment’ of BHWs, has a key role in improving the quality of service. BHWs who possess *organizational commitment* can determine whether to continue or discontinue their organizational membership, which may determine the success of any organization.

Also, a crucial influence on the service quality of the workers within the company also exists. A committed workforce provides critical advantages to the company, such as lesser worker turnover and higher productivity. Due to this, most companies invested substantially in commitment. The result is similar to the findings of Abdul-Majid, Anwar, Fahd, Gilal, Pahi, Talpur, and Waqas (2022) that a significant link exists between ‘organizational commitment and service quality’. As a result, it recommended that organizations must focus on the employees’ *organizational commitment* to enhance *service delivery*.

Also, the finding is consistent with the study of Yengfei, Mengze, and Ki-Hyung (2022), who said that quality commitment is essential for organizations to achieve the most critical determinant of service delivery through which commitment and the willingness to give quality service to customers are prerequisites in achieving high quality service performance. Likewise, in another study it was found out that both management and employees who are committed to their work positively affect their satisfaction and customer service (Adam, Erfivan, & Kesuma, 2022).

Significance of the Relationship between Workplace Spirituality and Service Quality of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

Table 5.2 shows that the computed R-value of 0.543 with less than 0.05 P-value indicated the rejection of null hypothesis. Based on the measurement, all the workplace spirituality indices strongly correlate with service quality of BHWs, which only means that the data show a significant relationship between variables.

Table 5.2: Significance of the Relationship between Workplace Spirituality and Service Quality of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

Workplace Spirituality	Service Quality					
	Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Empathy	Tangibles	Overall
Compassion	.311** .000	.296** .000	.328** .000	.312** .000	.184** .000	.380** .000
Meaning Work	.393** .000	.346** .000	.336** .000	.406** .000	.151** .001	.424** .000
Transcendence	.353** .000	.312** .000	.327** .000	.359** .000	.144** .002	.388** .000
Mindfulness	.394** .000	.407** .000	.423** .000	.512** .000	.293** .000	.546** .000
Overall	.452** .000	.425** .000	.443** .000	.495** .000	.242** .000	.543** .000

Workplace spirituality enhances service quality which is not just significant, but crucial. It serves as an urgent antidote to negative environments such as employee burnout, a need that has become increasingly apparent in the face of modern challenges. A spiritual workplace not only fosters organizational trust but also enhances positive attitudes and beliefs, stressing the urgency of its implementation.

The data of Jin and Lee (2020) supported the findings, who said that *workplace spirituality* establishes a positive link between the public health system and the community. A high degree of *workplace spirituality* among healthcare providers exist because of its meaning and purposed provided to the employees. Workplace support in spiritual care brings about a positive provision of care to the patients of nurses, resulting in longer tenure and having a therapeutic effect on patients and families. An increased spiritual value positively influences the services, thus supported by the study of Rajain and Rathee (2020). They concluded that the workforce would have better organizational performance, job involvement, commitment, and satisfaction because of spiritual care or *workplace spirituality* within the organization.

Significance of the Relationship between Team Effectiveness and Service Quality of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

The data in Table 5.3 showed a computed R-value of 0.725 with less than 0.05 P-value, which portrays that the null hypothesis was rejected. It reveals that there is a correlation between *team effectiveness* and *service quality* of BHWs. Hence, a significant relationship between variables exists.

Team effectiveness has been shown to have significant implications for *service quality* which is a critical factor in building *service quality* due to increasing complexity, specialization, ‘co-morbidities, chronic disease, global workforce shortages, and safe working hours initiatives. Reliable teamwork is essential in the delivery of safe, high-quality care demands.

Table 5.3: Significance of the Relationship between Team Effectiveness and Service Quality of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

Team Effectiveness	Service Quality					
	Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Empathy	Tangibles	Overall
Effective Decision-making	.405** .000	.403** .000	.377** .000	.395** .000	.295** .000	.507** .000
Open Communication	.430** .000	.372** .000	.456** .000	.457** .000	.239** .000	.518** .000
Support and Trust	.393** .000	.357** .000	.366** .000	.426** .000	.333** .000	.514** .000
Honesty	.333** .000	.301** .000	.343** .000	.377** .000	.310** .000	.459** .000
Effective Leadership	.374** .000	.281** .000	.347** .000	.347** .000	.271** .000	.442** .000
Opportunities for Development	.485** .000	.387** .000	.471** .000	.466** .000	.287** .000	.560** .000
Effective Inter-team Relationship	.429** .000	.403** .000	.398** .000	.449** .000	.291** .000	.530** .000
Feedback	.483** .000	.408** .000	.502** .000	.467** .000	.353** .000	.600** .000
Clear Understanding of Aims and Objectives	.459** .000	.466** .000	.442** .000	.462** .000	.315** .000	.576** .000
Conflict Management	.309** .000	.340** .000	.357** .000	.402** .000	.302** .000	.469** .000
Overall	.572** .000	.520** .000	.568** .000	.595** .000	.421** .000	.725** .000

The results align with the study of Chakraborty, Kaynak, and Pagan (2021), who emphasized that healthcare quality needs teamwork fed by support, trust, and feedback. The morale, confidence, and competence developed by the team will affect patient care, especially the essential services in the community... Effective teamwork and technology integration are the two critical factors that drive high-quality healthcare service delivery. Still, the role of hospital leadership quality is an essential determinant for teams to work effectively in healthcare settings. From the findings of Brom, Kang, Lasater, and McHugh (2021), there is a correlation between ‘*team effectiveness and service quality*’, particularly in healthcare, where higher nurse-physical teamwork resulted in improved patient outcomes for *service quality*.

Effect of Organizational Commitment, Workplace Spirituality and Team Effectiveness on Service Quality of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

Table 6 shows the ‘*effect of organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, as well as, team effectiveness to service quality of BHWs*’. Based on the data, the computed F-value=168.201, R-value=0.726, R² value=.527, and p-value=.000, in which it is lower than the 0.05 level of

significance; hence, the null hypothesis was rejected where it underscores the influence of the three variables to the service quality of BHWs.

Table 6: Significance of the Influence of Organizational Commitment, Workplace Spirituality and Team Effectiveness on Service Quality of Barangay Health Workers in Region XII

Service Quality		<i>B</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
(Variables)					
Constant		1.780		12.904	.000
Organizational Commitment		-.003	-.004	-.102	.919
Workplace Spirituality		.063	.073	1.480	.140
Team Effectiveness		.572	.676	14.550	.000
R	.726				
R ²	.527				
ΔR	.524				
F	168.201				
ρ	.000				

The data in Table 6 show that ‘*organizational commitment*’ had coefficients =-.003 and -.004 (standardized and unstandardized), t-value=-.102 and p-value=.919 (non-significant); ‘*workplace spirituality*’ had coefficients=.063 and .073 (standardized and unstandardized), t-value=1.480 and p-value=.140 (non-significant); and ‘*team effectiveness*’ showed coefficients=.572 and .676 (standardized and unstandardized), t-value=14.550, and p-value=.000 (Significant).

Consequently, the regression model showed that $R^2 = .527$ with the combination of influence on *service quality*, which signifies that the ‘predictor variables’ (‘*organizational commitment*’, *workplace spirituality*, and *team effectiveness*’), illustrate 52.7% of the variation in *service quality* of BHWs. The 47.3% of the variation could be the other factors that are not covered in this research.

The results of Buljac-Samardzic, Doekhie, and van Wijngaarden, (2020) is consistent with the finding of the study, which underscores the importance of teamwork in healthcare organizations for the provision of quality of service. This highlights the urgent need for team improvement, which can be achieved through team interventions. The study is supported by the statement of Jain, Hiranmou, and Upadhyal (2020), who advocated for a customer-centric view of healthcare *service quality* that includes patient safety and clinical effectiveness, apart from patient experience, and focuses on compassion, dignity, and respect.

Best Fit Model of Service Quality

Table 7 shows that there were ‘three models generated to obtain the *best-fit model*’ of the *service quality of BHWs*. Based on the given fit criteria which was used for the models’ acceptance and rejection, *Model 3* met all the indices. The goodness of fit measures should meet the given requirements: (1) ‘p-value>0.05, (2) ‘Chi-square/degrees of freedom value 0<value<2, (3) ‘Goodness of Fit, Comparative Fit Index, Normed Fit Index, Tucker-Lewis Index must be

all >0.95 ’, (4) ‘Root Mean Square of Error Approximation value must be <0.05 ’, and (5) $p\text{-close}>0.05$.

Table 7: Summary of Goodness of Fit Measures of the Three Generated Models

Model	P-value (>0.05)	CMIN / DF (0<value<2)	GFI (>0.95)	CFI (>0.95)	NFI (>0.95)	TLI (>0.95)	RMSEA (<0.05)	P-close (>0.05)
1	.000	5.350	.829	.799	.764	.774	.098	.000
2	.000	3.479	.881	.886	.848	.871	.074	.000
3	.082	1.284	.978	.993	.971	.990	.025	.997

Legend:

- CMIN/DF – Chi Square/Degrees of Freedom (0<value<2)
- GFI – Goodness of Fit Index (>0.95)
- RMSEA – Root Mean Square of Error Approximation (<0.05)
- NFI – Normed Fit Index (>0.95)
- TLI – Tucker-Lewis Index (>0.95)
- CFI – Comparative Fit Index (>0.95)

Model 1 in Table 8 shows that ‘team effectiveness’ with the highest beta values (.672) has a strong link with ‘service quality’, followed by ‘workplace spirituality’ (beta=.125) while ‘organizational commitment’ (beta=.044^{NS}) does not have an effect to service quality. Table 7 shows that ‘organizational commitment, ‘workplace spirituality’, and team effectiveness’ are not predictors of service quality, with a $p\text{-value}=>0.05$. Also, revealed that the results of fit values were not within criteria, which means that it does not meet the fit standard.

Table 8: Regression Weights of the 3 Generated Models

Model	Exogenous Variables to Endogenous Variable		
	Organizational Commitment	Workplace Spirituality	Team Effectiveness
1	.044 ^{NS}	.125***	.672***
2	.073 ^{NS}	-.002 ^{NS}	.711***
3	-.240 ^{NS}	.130 ^{NS}	.831***

Moreover, Model 2 shows a strong correlation between team effectiveness and service quality. The variables - organizational commitment (beta=.073^{NS}) and workplace spirituality (beta=-.002^{NS}), do not affect service quality. Table 8 shows that team effectiveness has the highest beta value (.711); however, Model 2 failed to meet criteria.

Meanwhile, Generated Model 3 has a ‘p-value’=.082, ‘CMIN/DF’=1.284, ‘goodness of fit index’=.978, ‘comparative fit index’=.993, ‘normed fit index’=.971, ‘Tucker-Lewis index’=.990, ‘RMSEA’=.025, and ‘p-close’=.997. Hence, all ‘variables are fitted to the best-fit’ for the service quality of BHWs. It only means that the third model showed the causal relationship of organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, and team effectiveness and endogenous variable service quality.

Notably, the data revealed a rejection of the null hypothesis to which the model shows a correlation between organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, team effectiveness, and service quality among BHWs in the region. Hence, it can be surmised that the result instills confidence in the model robustness, which interconnects the given variables.

Legend:

- | | | |
|-----------------------------|--|---------------------|
| AFC- affective commitment | FEE- feedback | RES- Responsiveness |
| COC- continuance commitment | EIR - effective inter-team relationships | ASS- Assurance |
| TRA- transcendence | OPD- opportunities for development | EMP- Empathy |
| MEW - meaningful work | EDM- effective decision-making | |
| COM - compassion | REL- Reliability | |

Figure 2: Best Fit Model in Standard Solution

Figure 2 shows that two organizational commitment indicators, namely, ‘affective and continuance commitment, are service quality predictors. The workplace spirituality’s indicators

of transcendence, meaningful work, and compassion affect service quality. The predictors of team effectiveness have four out of ten indicators: feedback, effective inter-team relationships, opportunities for development, and effective decision-making that significantly affect service quality. Meanwhile, service quality, is measured based on reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.

The study of Abdul-Majid, Anwar, Fahd, Gilal, Pahi, Talpur, and Waqas (2022), Jin and Lee (2020) supports the results, all of which also demonstrated a direct link of organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, and team effectiveness on service quality.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The levels of organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, team effectiveness, and service quality of barangay health workers in Region XII are very high, and they are always manifested. It is recommended to provide benefits to barangay health workers (BHWs) to enhance their commitment to stay loyal to the organization by meeting their needs and ensuring their satisfaction through better working conditions, pay, incentives, opportunities for career advancement, effective leadership style, workgroup, and social relations, and good working conditions. By enhancing their commitment, the loyalty of the barangay health workers will be strengthened, resulting in gaining the trust of their clients and continuing their commitment.

There is a significant relationship between organizational commitment and service quality, workplace spirituality and service quality, and team effectiveness and service quality among barangay health workers of Region XII. The Department of Health (DOH) and the local government units (LGUs) should provide more support to the needs of the barangay health workers, such as better pay and privileges, and more training for growth to continue their services and improve the facilities for client satisfaction and the organization's success. Healthcare providers can enhance health outcomes and client satisfaction. Researching the connections and relationships among different variables is vital for healthcare organizations to understand better and meet client expectations.

They are also significant predictors of the endogenous variable service quality, with team effectiveness as the best predictor among the exogenous variables. It is recommended that administrators should focus on team interventions since these are crucial for improving performance outcomes such as effectiveness, efficiency, and client safety. Effective teamwork positively impacts client safety and is crucial due to the increasing complexity and specialization in healthcare. It is essential for teams to have specific roles, work together towards common goals. Organized feedback is essential for influential executives in a team or organization to avoid the negative impacts of sterile dogmatism.

The Generated Model 3 was found to be the best-fit model that meet the criteria of a reasonable fit. Therefore, it is considered the most efficient from the three models generated from the study. It is suggested that government agencies should focus more on making barangay health workers stay committed and enhance their spiritual relationship in the workplace. Committed workers improve service delivery by going above and beyond their duties. In healthcare,

fostering workplace spirituality improves client care and worker satisfaction.

The organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, and team effectiveness have direct link towards service quality of BHWs confirmed the Service Quality Gap Theory. Therefore, it is recommended that employee dedication and enthusiasm significantly impact client satisfaction and service quality. Prioritizing adaptability, teamwork, effective leadership, and decision-making are important of a better quality of service. Client retention is an indicator of service quality. Therefore, efforts should be made to enhance services while minimizing costs, emphasizing safety, effectiveness, client-centeredness, and timeliness.

The study results state that organizational commitment, workplace spirituality, and team effectiveness are predictors of service quality. Hence, it is suggested that the top officials may implement reforms to enhance the services provided by the BHWs through capacity building, and training initiatives. Moreover, the City Health Offices, LGUs, and other stakeholders may consider the results as a benchmark for reforms and future policies to strategize ways to promote the services of healthcare workers. The heads of the agencies may employ the study findings and the best-fit from the research in producing, revising, and institutionalizing agency guideline on improving healthcare workers' service quality programs at different levels per the acceptable standards.

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Declaration of Interest Statement

There is no conflict of interest.

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